

The Influence of Return On Equity (ROE) in Islamic Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research

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Abstract

This research aims to determine the effect of Return On Equity (ROE) in Sharia Banking with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in Library Research studies. The object of the research is Return On Equity (ROE) in Sharia Banking. The source of data collection comes from searching national journals indexed by Google Scholar and Sinta via the Perish/Harzing app. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the influence of ROE on Sharia Banking using bibliometric studies with the VOSviewer algorithm software; and (2) mapping influences and determinants Return on Equity (ROE) in Sharia Banking using a Library Research study. The research results show that based on the VOSviewer bibliometric study, research regarding the influence of Return On Equity (ROE) on Sharia Banking is divided into 7 clusters and 133 topic items. Meanwhile, based on a Library Research study, there are 2 The main theme is around Return On Equity (ROE) in Sharia Banking. The implication and contribution of this research is to map topics that are often researched by researchers, so that they can become a reference for subsequent researchers.

Keywords: Return on Equity (ROE), Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Library Research, Sharia Banking.

Introduction

ROE is one of the main indicators for evaluating a company's financial performance. The development of ROE in sharia banking has shown a positive trend over the last few years. Based on data from Bank Indonesia, the ROE of Islamic banking in Indonesia has increased from year to year, although there have been fluctuations in certain years. Positive asset growth shows that the company is developing and expanding its business. In the context of Islamic banking, asset growth can be influenced by an increase in the number of customers, increased demand for credit, or expansion into wider areas. Higher asset growth can have a positive impact on ROE because a company can generate more income from larger assets.

In previous research, high ROE can increase liquidity risk in Islamic banking, because banks may be too dependent on internal sources of financing such as retained earnings and equity. These internal sources of financing can become less liquid and difficult to access in situations of urgent funding needs. Therefore, Islamic banking needs to consider a balance between the use of internal and external financing sources to reduce liquidity risk. In 2020, the average ROE in sharia banking reached 10.22%, up from 8.88% in 2019. The increase in ROE in sharia banking can be caused by several factors, including: (1) The increasingly rapid growth of the sharia banking market provides great opportunities for banks to increase revenues and profits; (2) Islamic banks continue to make improvements in their operational efficiency, including in risk management and improving asset quality, which has a positive impact on their financial performance; (3) Sharia banks are also increasingly providing more comprehensive services for customers,

including developing products and services that comply with sharia principles. However, keep in mind that ROE is only one indicator of a company's financial performance. Therefore, it is important to evaluate company performance from various other aspects, such as Return on Assets (ROA), Net Interest Margin (NIM), and Non-Performing Financing (NPF). In sharia banking, liquidity risk can occur due to large withdrawals of funds by customers or the bank's inability to obtain funds from the financial market. High liquidity risk can reduce ROE because the company has to bear additional costs to obtain funds or has to sell assets at a lower price.

Library Research

Return On Equity (ROE) is a ratio used to measure a company's profits in generating returns on capital invested by shareholders. This ratio is an important indicator in evaluating a company's financial performance. In sharia banking, ROE is also used as an indicator of financial performance, but with sharia principles applied. For example, sharia banking does not provide interest to its customers because it violates sharia principles which prohibit usury. Therefore, profits are generated from administrative costs, profit sharing, and other services.

In Islamic banking, a high ROE indicates that the company has succeeded in generating good returns on the capital invested by shareholders. However, apart from ROE, there are also other financial ratios that need to be considered when assessing the financial performance of sharia banking, such as Return on Assets (ROA), Net Profit Margin (NPM), and so on. Apart from that, the aspect of compliance with sharia principles must also be considered in assessing the performance of sharia banking. However, it should be noted that Islamic banking has different characteristics from conventional companies, such as the use of sharia principles and different financial products. Therefore, in measuring ROE in sharia banking, certain adjustments need to be made in accordance with the characteristics and sharia principles adhered to by the bank.

Bibliometric research is the application of statistical and mathematical methods to analyze published articles and journals. The aim of bibliometric research is to examine and study maps of literary development in scientific publishing. This research could use more sophisticated multifaceted techniques to analyze simple productivity measures based on article citations. This research is also able to recognize and describe the development of new science and technology.

VOSviewer is bibliometric software used for visualization and analysis of scientific publication data. It allows users to visualize citation, co-citation, and co-word analysis data in the form of graphs and diagrams that are intuitive and easy to accept. VOSviewer can help researchers and analysts carry out citation network analysis, find relationships between scientific fields, and understand trends and issues in scientific literature. It also helps in determining future research directions and gaining insight into the performance and contributions of individuals, institutions, and scientific fields. VOSviewer has an easy-to-use user interface and can be used together with data coming from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. It allows users to visualize and analyze publication data effectively and efficiently.

Studies Library Research is a process that includes identification, evaluation, and synthesis of results from previous research on a specific topic. It aims to provide an overview of trends, issues, and advances in related fields and assist in understanding how previous research influences future research developments and directions. Library Research studies are usually conducted as part of the research process to ensure that researchers understand the existing research environment. It also helps in determining problems and gaps in the existing literature and helps

in the formulation of hypotheses and understanding of specific research areas. Library Research studies can be carried out by accessing scientific publication databases, such as Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. Researchers can also carry out manual searches through scientific journals and related books. Library Research studies must be carried out with a systematic and objective methodology to ensure that the results are accurate and valid.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in Library Research studies. The research object is Return On Equity (ROE). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on ROE in Sharia Banking.

The source of data collection comes from searching for accredited national journals Sinta 1-6 via the Perish/Harzing application. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer software. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key words " Return On Equity " and " ROE " over the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (2) mapping research topics based on Library Research studies (Budianto, 2022) .

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Return on Equity (ROE) in Sharia Banking

The reaction from searches for scientific journal publications regarding Return On Equity over a 10 year period, namely from 2012 to 2022, shows the development of journal publications every year, especially in the last 6 years. Data was obtained in the form of articles totaling 55 titles originating from the accredited national journal Sinta 1-6. It is recorded that in 2021, article publications will reach 10 titles. Therefore, the average publication of articles about ROE is 5 titles per year.

Table 1
Scientific publication data regarding Return On Equity by year

Year of Publication	Number of Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Articles
2010	1	2016	4	2020	7
2013	1	2017	5	2021	10
2014	1	2018	8	2022	5
2015	3	2019	8		
Total 55					

In table 2, there are 3 affiliates/institutions that publish the most articles about Return On Equity (ROE). The Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sharia Economics is the journal that publishes the most articles about ROE, namely 4 articles.

Table 2
Institutional Data and Journal Publishing Articles Return on Equity

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Number of Publications
Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sharia Economics	4
Diponegoro Journal of Management, Human Falah: Journal of Islamic Economics and Business Studies	2

Based on table 3, the most productive researcher is Nur Ahmadi Bi Rahmani, who published articles twice. Meanwhile, other researchers only wrote once about Return On Equity in Sharia Banking, namely:

Table 3
Article Author Data Return On Equity

Name and Affiliation	Number of Publications
Nur Ahmadi Bi Rahmani (North Sumatra State Islamic University)	2
Ilham Gibran Abdullah (Brawijaya University), Aisyah, Jaryono, Sulistyandasari (General Sudirman University), Rendra Akbar (Airlangga University), Cut Mia Rahmatul Ul Ya, Aliamin (Syiah Kuala University), Dewi Laraswati, Akbar Yusuf, Fitriningsih Amalo (Muhammadiyah University Malang), Agung Anugrah, Muhammad Syaichu, Farrashita Aulia, Prasetiono (Diponegoro University), Dian Shinta Arini, Fenty Fauziah (East Kalimantan Muhammadiyah University), Muhammad Ash-Shiddiqy (UIN Sunan Kalijaga Yogyakarta), Suci Handayani, Maizul Rahmizal, Khairil Aswan (KBP College of Economics, Padang), Febry Yani Zamzam Limesta, Dedi Wibowo (Marshal Suryadarma Aerospace University), Nofriyanti, Kamaluddin, Sry Lestari, Damri (IAIN Padangsidempuan)	1

Bibliometric Mapping Research Regarding Return On Equity (ROE)

Research results via website Garuda (Digital Reference Garba) is sent in the form of Research Information, entered and described using VOSviewer. The results are as follows:

Figure 1
Depiction of Relationships Map of Research Developments Regarding Return on Equity (ROE)

Co-word map, it shows the growth of research around Return On Equity p Sharia Banking is divided into 7 clusters and 133 topics, namely as follows:

Table 3
Bibliometric Visualization around Return On Equity (ROE)

Cluster No	Color	Number of Items	Topic
1	Red	30	b operating costs to operating income, bopo, capital adequacy ratio, capital structure, cash ratio, commercial bank, and debt, data collection, deposit ratio, documentation, factor, financial performance, form, Indonesian period, investor, Islamic commercial bank, ldr, liquidity risk, loan, negative effect, influence of return, profitability, purposive sampling, sample, sampling technique, secondary data, study, tcount, value.
2	Green	23	company size, data, der, influenced, earnings per share, eps, financial report, investment company, content, services, level, multiple linear regression analysis, company value, company, sample, service, share, sharia stock return, tattoo, registered, tobins q, firm size, variable.
3	Blue	21	a nnuual report, indonesian stock exchange, company, current ratio, and return, debt, dividend payout ratio, equity ratio, stock price, jakarta islamic index, panel data regression, per, population, price, ratio, sharia stock price, significant effect, stock price, stock return, sharia stock, total assets.
4	Yellow	20	b ank, bmt, condition, data analysis, dpk, equity, fund, influence, institution, mudharabah, mudharabah financing, musyarakah financing, profit, quantitative approach, research, significance value, significant influence, test, third party fund, type.
5	Purple	19	a analysis, sharia commercial banks, and the significance, effect, fdr, financing, income, Islamic bank, murabahah, musyarakah, non-performing financing, npf, ojk, performing financing, period, roe, t table, tbk, on returns.
6	Black	10	b ank Indonesia, data analysis techniqe, debt financing, equity financing, financial statement, gpm, net profit margin, npm, price change, sharia bank.
7	Orange	10	a technical analysis, asset, car, and financing, p value, in registered Indonesian sharia banking, return, roa, roce, against capital adequacy ratio.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Determinant Variables for Return on Equity/ROE in Sharia Banking

Library Research study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 31 determinant variables for Return On Equity/ROE, namely:

First, Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR. CAR is a ratio that measures a bank's ability to bear risks with the capital it has. The higher the CAR, the better the bank's financial position and the smaller the risk of bankruptcy. In this case, CAR has a positive influence on ROE because the greater the capital owned by sharia banking, the greater its ability to generate higher profits.

Second, Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR. FDR is a ratio that measures the amount of financing provided by the bank compared to the deposits received. The higher the FDR, the greater the liquidity risk for Islamic banking because too much financing is provided compared to deposits received. In this case, FDR has a negative influence on ROE because the greater the liquidity risk, the greater the possibility that the bank will have to pay higher interest, so that the profits generated will be reduced.

Third, Non Performing Financing/NPF. NPF is a ratio that measures the amount of problematic (uncollectible) financing compared to the total financing provided by the bank. The higher the NPF, the greater the credit risk for sharia banking due to the large amount of uncollectible financing. In this case, NPF has a negative influence on ROE because the greater the credit risk, the greater the possibility that the bank will have to bear losses on problematic financing, so that the resulting profit will be reduced.

Fourth, Operational Costs to Operational Income/BOPO. Operating Costs to Operating Income (BOPO) is a ratio that measures cost efficiency in generating income. The smaller the BOPO ratio, the better the bank's performance in managing its operational costs. In sharia banking, BOPO can affect ROE. The higher the BOPO ratio, the lower the ROE because high operational costs can affect the profits generated. Conversely, the lower the BOPO, the higher the ROE because the bank can generate higher profits from its revenues. Therefore, Islamic banking must pay attention to operational cost efficiency in order to increase ROE.

Fifth, Current Ratio. Current Ratio is a ratio that measures a bank's ability to pay its short-term obligations. The higher the Current Ratio, the better the bank's ability to pay its short-term obligations. In sharia banking, the Current Ratio can influence ROE. The higher the Current Ratio, the better the bank's performance in managing its liquidity. Good liquidity performance can help banks to generate higher profits from their investments. Therefore, Islamic banking must pay attention to the Current Ratio in order to increase ROE.

Sixth, Earnings Per Share/EPS. Earning Per Share (EPS) is a ratio that measures the net profit per share owned by shareholders. The higher the EPS, the greater the profit the company generates per share. In sharia banking, EPS can influence ROE. The higher the EPS, the better the bank's performance in generating profits. Higher profits can help banks to increase ROE. Therefore, Islamic banking must pay attention to EPS in order to increase ROE.

Seventh, Mudharabah, Musyarakah and Murabahah financing. Mudharabah financing is a type of financing where the bank provides funds and the customer provides labor and management. The profits generated are then shared between the bank and the customer at a previously agreed percentage. In this case, the effect of Mudharabah financing on ROE in sharia banking depends on the bank's ability to find good customers and manage funds effectively. If the bank can find good customers and manage funds effectively, the bank's ROE can increase. Musyarakah financing is a type of financing where the bank and customer both provide funds for a project or business, and profits are divided according to their respective ownership percentages. The effect of Musyarakah financing on ROE in sharia banking depends on the bank's ability to select potential projects or businesses and maintain good cooperative relationships with customers. If banks can select potential projects and

maintain good cooperative relationships with customers, the bank's ROE can increase. Murabahah financing is a type of financing where the bank buys goods at the customer's request and resells them at a higher price. The selling price includes a previously agreed profit margin. The effect of Murabahah financing on ROE in sharia banking depends on the bank's ability to determine the right selling price and manage credit risk well. If the bank can determine the right selling price and manage credit risk well, the bank's ROE can increase.

Eighth, Islamic Social Reporting/ISR. The implementation of ISR can have a positive impact on the ROE of Islamic banking. By providing more transparent and accountable information about the company's social and environmental activities, investors and customers can have more trust and confidence in the company's performance. This can strengthen the company's image and increase public trust, which in turn can increase the share value and ROE of the company.

Ninth, Debt Financing. Implementing debt financing can have a positive impact on Islamic banking ROE if done wisely. If a company can borrow money at an interest rate that is lower than the rate of return on the investment generated, then the company's ROE can increase. However, keep in mind that excessive use of debt financing can increase the risk of bankruptcy and reduce the company's ROE.

Tenth, Equity Financing. The implementation of equity financing can have a positive impact on Islamic banking ROE by strengthening the company's capital structure. By increasing the amount of its own capital, the company can reduce the debt to capital ratio (leverage) and increase investor confidence. This can increase the share value and ROE of the company.

Eleventh, Third Party Funds/DPK Mudharabah. Mudharabah DPK is funds deposited by customers in sharia banks to be invested in profitable businesses, where the customer and the bank share the profits from the investment in accordance with a predetermined agreement. Mudharabah DPK can influence ROE in sharia banking because the greater the number of Mudharabah DPK managed by the bank, the greater the bank's opportunity to invest and generate profits. Thus, Mudharabah DPK can increase ROE in sharia banking.

Twelfth, Liability of other institutions. Liabilities of Other Institutions are debts obtained by sharia banks from other institutions such as commercial banks, central banks, or other financial institutions. The influence of Liabilities of Other Institutions on ROE in Islamic banking can vary depending on the amount of interest that must be paid by the bank to take out the debt and the rate of return obtained from using the debt. If the interest that must be paid by the bank is lower than the returns obtained, then Liabilities of Other Institutions can increase ROE. However, if the interest that must be paid is higher than the returns obtained, then Liabilities of Other Institutions can reduce ROE.

Thirteenth, Debt to Equity Ratio/DER. DER is a ratio that measures the proportion of debt and equity used by a bank to fund its operations. The effect of DER on ROE in Islamic banking can also vary depending on the amount of interest that must be paid by the bank for the debt and the rate of return obtained from the use of debt and equity. If the return obtained from debt is higher than the interest that must be paid, then DER can increase ROE. However, if the interest that must be paid is higher than the return obtained, then DER can reduce ROE.

fourteenth, Net Profit Margin/NPM. Net Profit Margin (NPM) is a financial ratio used to measure the efficiency of a company in generating net profit from sales. NPM is calculated by dividing the company's net profit by total revenue or sales. The higher the NPM, the greater the company's ability to generate net profits from sales. Therefore, the higher the NPM, the higher the company's ROE. However, if the NPM

is too high, this can indicate an imbalance between the company's growth and efficiency, so that the company cannot maintain good growth in the long term.

fifteenth, Price Book Value/PBV. Price Book Value (PBV) is a financial ratio used to measure the market value of a company's shares compared to the company's book value or equity. PBV is calculated by dividing the market price of a company's shares by the company's book value per share. The higher the PBV, the higher investors' expectations of the company, and this can indicate that the company has good growth prospects. However, if the PBV is too high, this can indicate that the company's share price is too expensive compared to the company's book value, so there is a risk that the company's share price will fall in the future. In this case, the influence of PBV on ROE cannot be ascertained because ROE is influenced by other factors such as NPM and company assets.

sixteenth, Price Earning Ratio/PER. Price Earning Ratio (PER) is a financial ratio used to measure the market value of a company's shares compared to company profits. PER is calculated by dividing the market price of a company's shares by the company's profit per share. The higher the PER, the higher investors' expectations of the company, and this can indicate that the company has good growth prospects. However, if the PER is too high, this can indicate that the company's share price is too expensive compared to the company's profits, so there is a risk that the company's share price will fall in the future. In this case, the effect of PER on ROE cannot be ascertained because ROE is influenced by other factors such as NPM and company assets.

Seventeenth, Dividend Payout Ratio. Dividend Payout Ratio is a ratio that measures the percentage of a company's net profit paid to shareholders as dividends. In sharia banking, the Dividend Payout Ratio has an influence on Return on Equity (ROE) because dividends paid to shareholders are a source of income for shareholders, which in the end can increase the company's ROE. However, sharia banking has different principles in profit distribution, so the influence of the Dividend Payout Ratio on ROE in sharia banking can be different from conventional banking.

Eighteenth, company size. Company size also has an influence on ROE in sharia banking. Larger companies tend to have more resources and capital, so they can generate greater profits. However, in Islamic banking, company size is also related to the company's ability to offer more comprehensive products and services, which can ultimately increase ROE.

Nineteenth, Leverage causality. Leverage or debt ratio also has an influence on ROE in sharia banking. In the banking business, leverage can be used to increase ROE by borrowing money to increase available capital. However, too much debt can increase financial risk and affect ROE when profits decrease. In Islamic banking, the causality of leverage is related to sharia principles which prohibit the practice of usury and speculation, so the use of leverage needs to be controlled carefully to ensure compliance with sharia principles.

Twentieth, Gross Profit Margin/GPM. GPM is a ratio that measures a company's ability to generate profits from sales of products or services. High GPM indicates that the company can maintain high profit margins. In the context of Islamic banking, GPM can be influenced by several factors such as operational efficiency and the company's ability to set appropriate profit margins on the products and services offered. The higher the GPM in Islamic banking, the greater the possibility of a higher ROE.

Twenty-first, Liquidity risk. Liquidity risk is the risk when companies are unable to meet their financial obligations as they fall due. In sharia banking, liquidity risk can occur due to large withdrawals of funds by customers or the bank's inability to obtain funds from the financial market. High liquidity risk can reduce ROE

because the company has to bear additional costs to obtain funds or has to sell assets at a lower price.

Twenty-second, merger. A merger is a combination of two companies into one larger company. In the context of Islamic banking, mergers can provide several benefits such as operational efficiency, increased economies of scale, and increased market share. If a merger is done correctly, it can increase ROE because the larger company can take advantage of economies of scale and increase revenue.

Twenty-third, Total Asset Turn Over/TATO. TATO is a ratio that measures how efficiently a company uses its assets to generate sales. A higher TATO indicates that a company can generate more revenue with the same amount of assets. In the context of Islamic banking, TATO can be influenced by asset productivity and bank operational efficiency. The higher the TATO, the greater the likelihood of a higher ROE because the company can generate more revenue with the same assets.

Twenty-fourth, asset growth. Asset Growth is a measure of how quickly a company can increase its total assets over time. Positive asset growth shows that the company is developing and expanding its business. In the context of Islamic banking, asset growth can be influenced by an increase in the number of customers, increased demand for credit, or expansion into wider areas. Higher asset growth can have a positive impact on ROE because a company can generate more income from larger assets.

twenty fifth, Economic Value Added/EVA. EVA is a method used to measure the economic added value generated by a company. EVA measures the profits a company generates after considering the cost of capital used to fund its assets. In the context of Islamic banking, EVA can be influenced by the company's ability to generate profits above its cost of capital. The higher the EVA, the greater the possibility of a higher ROE because the company can generate higher profits compared to its cost of capital.

Twenty-sixth, Zakat funds. Well-managed zakat funds can help sharia banking increase its ROE. Zakat funds can be used to provide sharia financing to customers in need, thereby increasing bank income in the form of profit sharing. Apart from that, proper use of zakat funds can also help sharia banking improve asset quality and minimize credit risk which can affect ROE.

Twenty-seventh, Profit Sharing Financing. Profit Sharing Financing or financing with a profit sharing system is one of the main sources of income for sharia banking. In this system, banks and customers share profits according to a previously determined agreement. Thus, the greater the financing provided by sharia banking to customers with a profitable profit sharing system, the greater the opportunity to increase ROE.

twenty eight, Good Corporate Governance/GCG. GCG or good corporate governance is very important for sharia banking in creating a healthy and stable environment. In practice, GCG can help Islamic banking improve the quality of risk management, increase compliance with regulations, strengthen transparency and accountability, and build customer and public trust. All of these factors can contribute to increasing the ROE of Islamic banking.

Twenty-ninth, Bank Indonesia Sharia/SBIS Certificate. SBIS issuance can have a positive impact on Return On Equity (ROE) in sharia banking, because funds obtained through SBIS issuance have lower costs than other funding sources such as time deposits. This can increase the net profit of Islamic banking and therefore increase ROE.

Thirtieth, BI Rate. Changes in the BI Rate can affect ROE in sharia banking. If the BI Rate rises, funding costs for sharia banking will rise, which can reduce banking net profits and ROE. On the other hand, if the BI Rate decreases, funding

costs for sharia banking will decrease, thereby increasing net banking profits and ROE.

Thirty-one, inflation. Inflation can affect ROE in sharia banking because it can affect banking operational costs. If inflation is high, sharia banking operational costs will increase, such as fuel costs, labor wages and building maintenance costs. This can reduce banking net profits and ROE. On the other hand, if inflation is low, sharia banking operational costs will fall, thereby increasing net banking profits and ROE.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Influence of Return on Equity/ROE on Sharia Banking

Library Research study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 9 influences caused by Return On Equity/ROE, namely:

First, share prices. ROE is one of the main indicators of a company's financial performance. The higher the ROE of a company, the greater the possibility that the company will be able to provide good profits for its shareholders. Therefore, a high ROE tends to increase the company's share price. In sharia banking, a high ROE can also be a signal that the bank has succeeded in managing risk well and obtaining higher profits from invested capital. This can give investors confidence and encourage share prices to rise.

Second, stock returns. Stock returns are the profits obtained by shareholders of a company from the investments they make. A high ROE in Islamic banking can have a positive impact on stock returns, because a high ROE indicates that the company has succeeded in generating high profits from invested capital. However, the effect of ROE on stock returns is not always linear because it depends on other factors such as market conditions and competition in the banking industry.

Third, stock beta. Stock beta is a measure of the sensitivity of stock prices to market index movements. High ROE in Islamic banking tends to reduce stock beta. This is due to the fact that a high ROE indicates the stability of the company's financial performance and lower risks. Conversely, a low ROE tends to increase the stock's beta because it is considered to have a higher risk.

Fourth, Murabahah financing. Return on Equity (ROE) is a financial performance indicator used to measure how effective a bank is in utilizing its capital to generate profits. In sharia banking, ROE can influence murabahah financing because banks will be more inclined to provide such financing if the ROE is high. This is because banks will prioritize financing that provides greater profits to increase their ROE.

Fifth, company value. ROE also affects company value. The higher the ROE, the greater the company value. This is because ROE shows how effective the company is in generating profits from the capital it owns. In Islamic banking, company value can increase if the ROE is high because ROE is one of the factors taken into account by investors and analysts in determining the value of a company.

Sixth, profit growth. ROE can also influence a company's profit growth. The higher the ROE, the greater the company's profit growth. This is because ROE shows how effective the company is in generating profits from the capital it owns. In sharia banking, profit growth can increase if the ROE is high because ROE is one of the factors that can influence the increase in company profits.

Seventh, capital structure. Return On Equity (ROE) is a measure of the profits generated by a company compared to the owner's capital. In sharia banking, ROE can influence the capital structure, because sharia banks usually use owner's capital (equity) and third party funds (Mudharabah) as sources of financing. The higher the ROE, the greater the possibility that the bank will be able to obtain capital

from internal sources, thereby reducing the level of dependence on loans from third parties, so that the capital structure will be lighter.

Eighth, the level of profit sharing on Mudharabah deposits. Mudharabah deposits are a sharia banking product that provides profit sharing to depositors. The Mudharabah Deposit Profit Sharing Level is determined by the bank based on the amount of profit generated from the bank's operational activities. A high ROE indicates that the bank is able to generate greater profits from its operational activities, so that it can provide a higher level of profit sharing on Mudharabah deposits.

Ninth, liquidity risk. A high ROE can increase liquidity risk in Islamic banking, because banks may be too dependent on internal sources of financing such as retained earnings and equity. These internal sources of financing can become less liquid and difficult to access in situations of urgent funding needs. Therefore, Islamic banking needs to consider a balance between the use of internal and external financing sources to reduce liquidity risk.

Conclusions, Limitations, and Suggestions

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, the number of research publications surrounding Return On Equity/ROE in Sharia Banking during the period 2010 to 2022, shows a significant increase from year to year. The total number of publications is 55 research articles, which come from accredited national journals, Sinta. Second, the affiliate/institution that publishes the most research results is the Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sharia Economics, with 4 articles. Third, the most productive researcher is Nur Ahmadi Bi Rahmani, who published 2 journal articles. Fourth, there is mapping visualization using VOSviewer, research developments regarding Return On Equity/ROE in Sharia Banking divided into 7 clusters and 55 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 30 topics, cluster 2 consists of 23 topics, cluster 3 consists of 21 topics, cluster 4 consists of 20 topics, cluster 5 consists of 19 topics, cluster 6 consists of 10 topics, and cluster 7 consists of 10 topics. Fifth, based on the Library Research, there are 2 main research themes, namely: (1) Determinant variables; and (2) The impact caused.

Limitations

The scope of the research only covers the influence of Return On Equity (ROE) on Sharia Banking during the period 2010 to 2022. The publications studied only come from accredited national journals Sinta 1-6. These limitations mean that this research does not yet describe the influence of ROE on banking as a whole, both Sharia and Conventional Banking. Apart from that, there are several international journals indexed by Scopus that have not been included in this research, whereas these journals are needed to compare the influence of ROE in Indonesia and other countries.

Suggestion

It is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, both from national accredited journals Sinta and international journals indexed by Scopus, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer time span for research data so that it can The following research results were obtained: First, it is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization. Second, the results of the Library Research study can be explained in a more complex way.

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Appendix I

YEAR	JOURNAL TITLE & LINK (RETURN ON EQUITY IN SHARIA BANKING)
2010	ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF RETURN ON EQUITY, CURRENT RATIO, DEBT RATIO, OPERATING LEVERAGE AND ASSET GROWTH ON THE BETA OF SHARIA STOCK ON THE INDONESIAN STOCK EXCHANGE
2013	ANALYSIS OF DEBT TO EQUITY RATIO (DER), RETURN ON ASSETS (ROA), RETURN ON EQUITY (ROE), NET PROFIT MARGIN (NPM) ON STOCK PRICE IN SHARIA STOCK COMPANIES IN THE FOOD AND BEVERAGE SECTOR FOR THE 2013-2016 PERIOD
2014	Analysis of Financing To Deposit Ratio, Debt To Equity Ratio, Return On Equity And Quick Ratio Of Murabahah Financing In Sharia Commercial Banks In Indonesia
2015	ANALYSIS OF NON PERFORMING FINANCING MURABAHAH FINANCING IN RELATION TO RETURN ON EQUITY AT PT. MANDIRI SHARIA BANK

2015	<u>Analysis of the Effect of Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) and Financing to Deposit Ratio (FDR) on Return On Assets (ROA) and Return On Equity (ROE) in Sharia Commercial Bank Companies in Indonesia</u>
2015	<u>Analysis of the Effect of Non Performing Financing (NPF), Financing to Deposit Ratio (FDR), Operational Costs on Operating Income (BOPO) and Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) on Return on Equity (ROE) in Sharia Commercial Banks in Indonesia for the 2016 – 2020 Period</u>
2016	<u>ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF NON PERFORMING FINANCING MUDHARABAH FINANCING, NON PERFORMING FINANCING MUSYARAKAH FINANCING, AND NON PERFORMING FINANCING MURABAHAH FINANCING ON PROFITABILITY USING THE RETURN ON EQUITY APPROACH (Study of Sharia Commercial Banks in Indonesia)</u>
2016	<u>ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECT OF MUDHARABAH AND MUSYARAKAH FINANCING ON PROFITABILITY LEVELS (RETURN ON EQUITY) (Study of Sharia Commercial Banks Registered with Bank Indonesia for the 2009-2012 Period)</u>
2016	<u>ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF MUDHARABAH, MUSYARAKAH AND MURABAHAH FINANCING ON RETURN ON EQUITY OF SHARIA COMMERCIAL BANK</u>
2016	<u>ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF CAPITAL ADEQUACY RATIO (CAR), NON PERFORMING FINANCING (NPF), FINANCING TO DEPOSIT RATIO (FDR), AND OPERATIONAL EFFICIENCY RATIO (REO) ON RETURN ON EQUITY (ROE) OF SHARIA COMMERCIAL BANKS IN INDONESIA (PERIOD 2010-2014)</u>
2017	<u>Analysis of the Effect of Return on Equity and Company Size on Capital Structure in Sharia Banks in Indonesia for the 2010 - 2017 Period</u>
2017	<u>ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF RETURN ON EQUITY, DEBT TO EQUITY RATIO, CURRENT RATIO, AND PRICE TO BOOK VALUE ON SHARIAH STOCK RETURNS (Case Study of Companies Listed in the Jakarta Islamic Index for the 2011-2015 Period)</u>
2017	<u>PROFITABILITY ANALYSIS OF SHARIA COMMERCIAL BANK USING RETURN ON ASSET (ROA) AND RETURN ON EQUITY (ROE) RATIO</u>
2017	<u>Analysis of Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), Return on Capital Employed (ROCE) on Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) in Indonesian Sharia Banking</u>
2017	<u>Analysis of Return on Equity, Return on Assets, FDR, Bopo and Interest Rates on Mudharabah Deposit Levels (Sharia Commercial Bank Study 2012-2014)</u>
2017	<u>Causality Relationship between Leverage, Return on Equity, Earning Per Share, Company Size and Company Value in Property, Real Estate and Building Construction Sector Companies Listed on the Indonesian Sharia Stock Index (ISSI)</u>
2017	<u>Loan To Deposit Ratio, Capital Adequacy Ratio, Return On Equity And Bopo In Assessing The Financial Performance Of Pt. Bni Syariah Bank</u>
2018	<u>THE INFLUENCE OF CAR, FDR, NPF, AND BOPO ON PROFITABILITY (RETURN ON EQUITY) (Empirical Study of Sharia Commercial Banks in Indonesia for the 2009-2013 Period)</u>
2018	<u>THE INFLUENCE OF CURRENT RATIO, DEBT TO EQUITY RATIO, AND BOPO ON CAPITAL ADEQUACY RATIO WITH RETURN ON ASSETS AS INTERVENING VARIABLES IN SHARIA BANKING COMPANIES IN INDONESIA</u>
2018	<u>THE INFLUENCE OF CURRENT RATIO, EARNINGS PER SHARE (EPS), RETURN ON EQUITY (ROE), AND RETURN ON TOTAL ASSETS (ROA) ON STOCK PRICES IN PLANTATION SUB-SECTOR COMPANIES THAT ARE INCLUDED IN THE INDONESIA SHARIA STOCK INDEX (ISSI) CALCULATION ON THE INDONESIA STOCK EXCHANGE (BEI) PERIOD 2014 – 2017</u>

2018	<u>The Influence of Third Party Funds (DPK) Mudharabah Members and Liabilities of Other Institutions on Return on Equity (Study on Non-Bank Sharia Financial Institutions in Tulungagung and Blitar)</u>
2018	<u>The influence of debt financing and equity financing on return on equity in Islamic banks registered with Bank Indonesia</u>
2018	<u>THE INFLUENCE OF DEBT TO EQUITY RATIO, DIVIDEND PAYOUT RATIO AND RETURN ON ASSET ON SHARIA STOCK PRICES</u>
2018	<u>THE INFLUENCE OF DEBT TO EQUITY RATIO, EARNINGS PER SHARE, AND COMPANY SIZE ON SHARIA STOCK RETURNS IN COMPANIES LISTED ON THE JAKARTA ISLAMIC INDEX (JII) IN 2011-2015</u>
2018	<u>The Influence of Debt to Equity Ratio, Return on Equity, Earning Per Share on the Price Earning Ratio in Automotive Sector Companies Listed on the Indonesian Sharia Stock Index (ISSI) 2013-2017</u>
2019	<u>THE INFLUENCE OF FUNDAMENTAL FACTORS (CURRENT RATIO, RETURN ON ASSET, RETURN ON EQUITY, TOTAL ASSET TURN OVER, DEBT TO EQUITY RATIO, AND ASSET GROWTH) ON THE BETA OF SHARIA SHARES ON THE INDONESIAN STOCK EXCHANGE</u>
2019	<u>THE INFLUENCE OF FINANCING DEPOSIT RATIO (FDR), RETURN ON EQUITY (ROE), CAPITAL ADEQUACY RATIO (CAR) AND NON PERFORMING FINANCING (NPF) ON MURABAHAH FINANCING IN SHARIA COMMERCIAL BANKS IN INDONESIA FOR THE 2015-2019 PERIOD</u>
2019	<u>The Influence of Financing to Deposit Ratio, Non Performing Financing, and Return on Equity on Mudharabah Financing in Sharia Commercial Banks in Indonesia</u>
2019	<u>The Influence of Islamic Social Reporting on Profitability (Return on Assets and Return on Equity) in Sharia Commercial Banks in Indonesia</u>
2019	<u>THE EFFECT OF MURABAHAH AND MUSYARAKAH FINANCING CONTRIBUTIONS ON PROFITABILITY LEVELS (RETURN ON EQUITY) (Study of Sharia BPRs in the East Java Region Registered with Bank Indonesia for the 2010-2013 Period)</u>
2019	<u>THE INFLUENCE OF NON PERFORMING FINANCING (NPF), FINANCING TO DEPOSIT RATIO (FDR) and CAPITAL ADQUACY RATIO (CAR) ON RETURN ON EQUITY (ROE) OF SHARIA BANK</u>
2019	<u>THE INFLUENCE OF MUDHARABAH AND MUSYARAKAH FINANCING ON RETURN ON EQUITY AT PT. SHARIA COMMUNITY FINANCING BANK IN INDONESIA</u>
2019	<u>THE INFLUENCE OF MUDHARABAH FINANCING ON THE RATE OF RETURN ON EQUITY (ROE) IN SHARIA BANKS REGISTERED AT BANK INDONESIA</u>
2020	<u>The Influence of Price Earning Ratio (PER), Price Book Value (PBV) and Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) on Stock Returns (Study of Property and Real Estate Companies Listed on the Indonesian Sharia Stock Index)</u>
2020	<u>The influence of price earnings ratio, debt equity ratio, and return on equity on sharia stock prices for the 2017-2019 period</u>
2020	<u>THE INFLUENCE OF LIQUIDITY RATIO ON RETURN ON EQUITY IN SHARIA COMMERCIAL BANKS IN INDONESIA</u>
2020	<u>THE INFLUENCE OF RETURN ON ASSET (ROA), RETURN ON EQUITY (ROE) AND EARNINGS PER SHARE (EPS) ON SHARIA STOCK PRICES: Case Study of PT. Aneka Tambang Persero Tbk 2013-2017</u>
2020	<u>THE INFLUENCE OF RETURN ON ASSET (ROA), RETURN ON EQUITY (ROE), OPERATIONAL COSTS ON OPERATIONAL INCOME (BOPO) AND LOAN TO</u>

	<u>DEPOSIT RATIO (LDR) ON CAPITAL ADEQUACY RATIO (CAR) (Comparative Study of Conventional Banks and Sharia Commercial Banks</u>
2020	<u>THE INFLUENCE OF RETURN ON ASSET AND DEBT TO EQUITY RATIO ON THE VALUE OF SHARIA BANK COMPANIES BEFORE THE MERGER (Case Study of PT Bank BRI Syariah, Tbk in January-November 2020)</u>
2020	<u>The Influence of Return on Assets, Equity, and Bank Size on Liquidity Risk in Sharia Banks in Indonesia</u>
2021	<u>The Influence of Return On Assets, Market Value Added and Debt To Equity Ratio on Sharia Stock Returns</u>
2021	<u>THE INFLUENCE OF RETURN ON ASSET, RETURN ON EQUITY, AND FINANCING TO DEPOSIT RATIO ON THE LEVEL OF PROFIT SHARING OF MUDHARABAH DEPOSITS: In Sharia Commercial Banks for the 2012-2017 Period</u>
2021	<u>The Influence of Return On Assets (ROA), Return On Equity (ROE), Net Profit Margin (NPM), and Gross Profit Margin (GPM) on Sharia Banking Share Prices for the 2014-2018 Period</u>
2021	<u>THE INFLUENCE OF RETURN ON ASSETS (ROA), RETURN ON EQUITY (ROE), NET PROFIT MARGIN (NPM), AND GROSS PROFIT MARGIN (GPM) ON SHARIA BANKING STOCK PRICES FOR THE 2014-2018 PERIOD</u>
2021	<u>THE INFLUENCE OF RETURN ON ASSETS, DEBT TO EQUITY RATIO, CURRENT RATIO ON COMPANY STOCK RETURNS IN THE INDONESIAN SHARIA STOCK INDEX</u>
2021	<u>THE INFLUENCE OF RETURN ON ASSETS, RETURN ON EQUITY, AND EARNINGS PER SHARE ON COMPANY STOCK PRICES IN THE INDONESIAN SHARIAH STOCK INDEX LISTING (Trade, Services and Investment Sub-Sector 2015-2018)</u>
2021	<u>The Influence of Return On Equity (ROE), Debt To Equity Ratio (DER), and Price Earning Ratio (PER) on Stock Returns in Infrastructure, Utility and Transportation Companies on the Sharia Securities List for the 2017-2018 Period</u>
2021	<u>The Effect of Return on Equity and Economic Value Added on Company Value (Case Study of a Company That Issues Shares on the Sharia Securities List)</u>
2021	<u>The Influence of Return on Equity, Earning Per Share and Debt to Equity Ratio on Sharia Stock Prices</u>
2021	<u>The Influence of Return On Equity, Earning Per Share, and Debt to Equity Ratio on Stock Returns (Study of Sharia Stock Issuers in the Property and Real Estate Sector Registered with ISSI in 2013-2015)</u>
2022	<u>The Influence of Company Size, Total Asset Turnover, Return On Assets, Current Ratio, Debt To Equity Ratio, and Earning Per Share on Sharia Stock Returns in Trading, Services and Investment Companies Listed on the Indonesia Sharia Stock Index (ISSI) for the 2012-2015 Period</u>
2022	<u>SHARIA FINANCING PRODUCT RATIO AS A DETERMINANT OF RETURN ON EQUITY OF SHARIA COMMERCIAL BANK IN INDONESIA</u>
2022	<u>Return On Equity: Allocation of Zakat Funds, Profit Sharing Financing and Good Corporate Governance in Sharia Commercial Banks in Indonesia</u>
2022	<u>THE EFFECT OF MUDHARABAH AND MUSYARAKAH FINANCING ON RETURN ON EQUITY IN SYARIAH BANKS IN INDONESIA</u>
2022	<u>The Effect of Non Performing Financing (NPF) and Operating Expenses of Operating Income (BOPO) on Return on Equity (ROE) on PT. Bank Bri Syariah, Tbk.</u>